

TU Delft Software Carpentry Workshop

Coordinator Information Sheet

The **Coordinator** is responsible for the organisation of the [Carpentries](#) workshop and the facilitation during the online workshop. During an online workshop, the Coordinator plays the crucial role of keeping track of the time and being in charge of the technicalities to allow the Helpers and Instructors to really focus on their roles. Below the responsibilities of the Coordinator are listed in chronological order: before, during and after the workshop.

Before the workshop

- As TU Delft organises [self-organised workshops](#), the organisation of a workshop starts with the **recruitment of Instructors** and the planning of the workshop's **dates**.
- Send a **calendar invite** with the coordination programme (see **Appendix A**), the collaborative document (see **Appendix B**) and the Zoom details to the Instructors and potential Helpers. Calendar invites ensure that the dates and times are clearly communicated.
- Ensure that the **workshop website** is set up. The website is based on the Carpentries template (<https://github.com/carpentries/workshop-template>) which is forked to our repository (<https://github.com/4TUResearchData-Carpentries>) by either the Coordinator or one of the Instructors.
- After the workshop website has been updated with the correct information (Instructors, Helpers, dates, times, schedule and workshop goals), the workshop can be **registered with the Carpentries** (<https://amy.carpentries.org/forms/self-organised/>).
 - To avoid disappointment and a lot of external inquiries, request that the website is not publicly listed if the workshop is not open to external participants.
- Handle any **inquiries** about the workshop.
- Organise the **preparation meeting** of ~1 hour, hosted ~1 month in advance.
 - Make sure Instructors and Helpers have the opportunity to introduce themselves.
 - Go over the programme with the Instructors (set up the draft based on previous workshops) and discuss any adjustments.
 - Notify the Instructor that any adjustments can be made a week before their session.
 - Make sure that everyone is comfortable with their role during the workshop. Address any questions and concerns.
 - If needed, offer to do a test round of teaching and/or the teaching set up.

- When helpers are new, they may need a 1-on-1 meeting to prepare them for the workshop. They may also familiarise themselves with the role through the [Helpers information sheet](#).
- Send any **Helper information** for the relevant sessions in a concise email to the Helpers. This should be done a week in advance to allow the Helpers enough time to prepare.
 - Include information to the **Slack** workspace in the email and check whether all Helpers are in the workshop channel.
- Take care of the information that is sent out to the **participants**.
 - Make sure that information about the workshop is available in time for the participants to register (**Appendix C**).
 - Two weeks before the workshop starts, a pre-workshop email is sent out. This email allows participants to still deregister if needed as well as providing them with enough time to go through the software installations.
- Check if the **collaborative note document** is up to date.
 - Include information about the Instructors and Helpers.
- Check whether the participants have filled out the **pre-workshop survey**. If there is not enough response the link should be shared again in the workshop itself to improve the response rate.

During the workshop

- Start the Zoom meeting.
 - Ensure that each Instructor/Helper has renamed themselves to reflect their role and has been made a co-host, e.g. add “(Helper)” or “(Notes)” in front of their names.
 - Ensure that all participants are able to share their screens: this is crucial for trouble shooting in breakout rooms.
 - Make sure that the Instructor has had a chance to test their setup.
 - Go over any remaining introductions and final checks before the participants are admitted to the Zoom room.
- Start the Workshop and introduce the session:
 - Introduce The Carpentries and 4TU.ResearchData.
 - Introduce the Code of Conduct and ensure it is followed.
 - Introduce the session’s team.
 - Introduce Zoom.
 - Introduce the ways that learners can ask for help.
 - Show the programme of the day.
 - Start with the roll call and icebreaker.
- Remind the learners about filling in the pre- and post-workshop surveys.
- Keep track of the timing of the programme, remind the Instructor about the time (if needed) and regulate the breaks.

- Take care of technical difficulties and create and assign breakout rooms.
- Facilitate questions by learners and mute people when needed.
- Ensure that all the questions in the chat or the collaborative document are answered by the Helpers.
- Ask the learners for feedback through a separate Google Doc Feedback document.

After the workshop

- Coordinate the feedback session after each workshop session.
 - Ensure that the Instructors and Helpers go over the feedback from the participants to see if any adjustments to the programme are needed for the following sessions.
 - Each Instructor should also receive feedback from the Helpers.
 - All voices should be heard. This can be done verbally or through another collaborative document with Helper feedback, which is also available during the workshop so that Helpers can already provide their feedback during the workshop.
- Make sure that the post-workshop communication is taken care of.
 - Send out an email (see **(Appendix D)**) to the participants with extra resources, reminding that the collaborative document can be downloaded with instructions, share notebooks of the Instructors and any screenshots taken during the workshop (with the use purposes listed), and a reminder to fill out the post workshop survey.
 - The last action on the list is to check the responses on the post-workshop survey. If the response rate is low, another reminder has to be sent out.

Based on our experience, it takes approximately ~12 hours of the Coordinators time to organise a single workshop, next to the ~20 hours of workshop attendance. This time decreased when materials and routines became more standardised. Some administration and management support is available by a student assistant (Lauren Besselaar, Femke van Giessen), who sends out the pre-workshop email and post-workshop survey reminder for each workshop and for some of the workshops the student assistant keeps track of the registrations.

Set up by: Esther Plomp ([0000-0003-3625-1357](tel:0000-0003-3625-1357)), Emmy Tsang ([0000-0002-9248-1280](tel:0000-0002-9248-1280)), and Paula Martinez Lavanchy ([0000-0003-1448-0917](tel:0000-0003-1448-0917)).

How to cite: Plomp, E., E. Tsang, P. Martinez Lavanchy. 2021-07-23. TU Delft Software Carpentry Workshop Coordinator Information Sheet, version 1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5126727>.

Appendix A: Template for the coordination programme

Software Carpentry Workshop: Coordination and program - ****add dates****

Website: ****add link to website ****

CoachView registrations: ****add amount of participants ****

Google Docs: Used during the workshop to communicate programme/exercises/commands used ****add link to Google Docs****

Zoom explanation: ****add link to Zoom introduction slides****

Survey results: ****add link to the Carpentries Survey results****

Feedback from participants: ****add link to Feedback document for participants ****

Feedback from Helpers: ****add link to Feedback document for Helpers**

Day 1 – ****add date**** - Unix Shell - Instructor: ****add
Instructor****

Materials

<http://swcarpentry.github.io/shell-novice/>

****add link to materials****

Zoom

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode ****

People

Helpers: (~6 helpers)

Googledoc: ****add Helpers (Code documenter)****

Chat, Breakout rooms: ****add Helpers (Troubleshooter)****

Observers: ****add observers****

Program

12.45 - Organisers/Instructors/Helpers in the Zoom meeting room

13:00 - Troubleshooting (if needed - GitBash)

13:15 - Welcome and introduction - Coordinator

- The Carpentries / Event sponsored by 4TU.Research data
- Reminder of Pre-workshop survey
- Presentation of Instructors and helper
- Introduction to Zoom and the tools to be used in the workshop
- Show the program of the day
- Ice breaker using Google Docs

13:30 - Introduction to the Unix Shell

- Introducing the Shell - Teaching 5 min
- Navigating Files and Directories - Teaching 30 min
- **Exercise in plenum** - Exploring More ls Flags - 2min
Answer examples here:
<http://swcarpentry.github.io/shell-novice/02-filedir/index.html>
- Working with Files and Directories - Teaching 30 min

14:20 - Coffee break

14:30 - **Exercise in Breakout rooms 1**- List filenames matching a pattern; Organizing Directories and Files; Reproduce a folder structure - 20 min

- ****add link to materials****

14:55 - Automating tasks with the Unix Shell

- Pipes and Filters - Teaching 30 min
- Loops - teaching 15 min

15:40 - Coffee break

15:50 - Automating tasks with the Unix Shell

- Shell Scripts (including for loop)- 25 min
- **Exercise in Breakout rooms 2**- Variables in Shell Scripts; Find the Longest File With a Given Extension - 20 min

****add link to materials here****

- Answer examples here:

<http://swcarpentry.github.io/shell-novice/06-script/index.html>

- (Finding Things - Teaching 5 min - if time allows)

16:50 - Last questions and reminder feedback

17:00 - End

17:00 - Sharing Feedback Instructors/Helpers

Day 2 – ****add date**** - Programming with Python -

Instructor: ****add Instructor****

Materials

<https://swcarpentry.github.io/python-novice-inflammation/>

****add link to materials****

Zoom

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode ****

People

Helpers: (~5 helpers)

Googledoc: ****add Helpers (Code documenter)****

Chat, Breakout rooms: ****add Helpers (Troubleshooter)****

Observers: ****add observers****

Program

12:45 - Organisers/Instructors/Helpers in the Zoom meeting room

13:00 - Troubleshooting (if needed)

13:15 - Welcome and instructions of the day - Coordinator

- Reminder Code of Conduct/How to get help
- Reminder on how to get help
- Programme of the day
- Ice breaker

13:30 - Introducing Python and Jupyter Notebooks (25 min)

Anaconda and Jupyter Lab/Notebooks

Jupyter Notebook features

13:55 - Variables (15 mins)

14:10 - Loading data in Python (30 mins)

Import and NumPy and display data

Slicing data

14:40 - **Coffee break** (15 min)

14:55 - Analysing data with Python (30 mins)

Basic statistics on data and a bit more on slicing data (10 min)

Exercises in Breakout Room (20 min)

****add link to materials****

15:25 - Visualizing Data (30 mins)

Matplotlib (15 mins)

Plotting (15 mins)

15:55 - Coffee break

16:10 - Repeating actions with FOR Loops (30 min)

Introducing For Loops (15 min)

Difference between Numpy arrays, Tuples, Lists and Strings (15 min)

16:40 - **Exercise in Breakout Room (15 mins)**

****add link to materials****

16:55 - Final questions for the day + reminder feedback - Coordinator

17:00 - End

17:00 - Sharing Feedback Instructors/Helpers

Day 3 – ****add date**** - Programming with Python - Instructor: ****add Instructor****

Materials

<https://swcarpentry.github.io/python-novice-inflammation/>

****add link to materials****

Zoom

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode ****

People

Helpers: (~5 helpers)

Googledoc: ****add Helpers (Code documenter)****

Chat, Breakout rooms: ****add Helpers (Troubleshooter)****

Observers: ****add observers****

Program

12.45 - Organisers/Instructors/Helpers in the Zoom meeting room

13:00 - Welcome and instructions of the day - Coordinator

- Reminder Code of Conduct/How to get help

- Programme of the day
 - Ice breaker
- 13:10 - Making choices with IF statements (20 min)
Recap of Day 3 (5 min)
Conditionals (15 min)
- 13:35 - User defined functions (40 min)
- 14:15 - **Exercise in Breakout Room (15 min)**
****add link to materials****
- 14.30 - Coffee break (15 min)**
- 14.45 - Errors and Exceptions (55 min)
Functions
Most common errors
Defensive programming
Command-Line Programs (25 min)
- 16.00 - Coffee break (15 min)**
- 16.15 - Command-Line Programs (35 min)
- 16:50 - Post workshop survey and feedback + download google doc + last questions -
Coordinator
- 17:00 - End
- 17:00 - Sharing Feedback Instructors/Helpers

Day 4 – ****add date**** - Git - Instructor: ****add Instructor****

Materials

<http://swcarpentry.github.io/git-novice/>

****add link to materials****

Zoom

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode****

People

Helpers: (~6 helpers)

Googledoc: ****add Helpers (Code documenter)****

Chat, Breakout rooms: ****add Helpers (Troubleshooter)****

Observers: ****add observers****

Program

12:45 - Organisers/Instructors/Helpers in the Zoom meeting room

13:00 - Troubleshooting (if needed - GitHub accounts)

13:10 - Welcome and instructions of the day - Coordinator

- Reminder Code of Conduct
- Reminder on how to get help
- Programme of the day
- Ice breaker -> **link to your GitHub account**

13:20 - Version control with Git

- Introduction to Automated Version Control - teaching 10 min
- Setting Up Git - teaching 5 min
- Creating a Repository - teaching 10 min
- Tracking Changes - teaching 25 min
- Ignoring Things - teaching 5 min

14:25 - Coffee break

14:40 - Version control with Git

- Exploring History & reverting changes
- Repo manipulation - exercise 15 min in **Breakout room**
 - Start from scratch, add files, update, recover old version
 - ****add link to exercise materials****
- Remotes in GitHub

15:45 - Coffee break

15:00 - Version control with Git

- Collaborating - teaching 30 min
- Conflicts: demonstration 10 mins

16:40 - Last questions and reminder Feedback - Coordinator

17:00 - End

17:00 - Sharing Feedback Instructors/Helpers

Zoom connections

Day 1 – ****add date****

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode ****

Day 2 – ****add date****

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode ****

Day 3 – ****add date****

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode ****

Day 4 – ****add date****

****add link****

Meeting ID: ****add ID****

Passcode: ****add Passcode ****

Feedback teaching

****add name of Instructor/Helper****

One thing that went very well

-
-

One thing that could be improved

-
-

Appendix B: Template for the collaborative notes

Software Carpentry Workshop TU Delft

****Add dates****

<https://data.4tu.nl/info/en/>

<https://carpentries.org/>

Code of Conduct

- Use welcoming and inclusive language
- Be respectful of different viewpoints and experiences
- Gracefully accept constructive criticism
- Focus on what is best for the community
- Show courtesy and respect towards other community members

https://docs.carpentries.org/topic_folders/policies/code-of-conduct.html

Instructors

****instructor names**** (see for pictures/more info ****add link****)

Contact your Faculty's Data Steward [here](#).

Contact the DCC [here](#).

Helpers

****Helper names**** (see for pictures/more info ****add link****)

Working with Zoom

See instruction slides ****add link****.

Getting help

- There are icons if you select the reactions list:
 - go slower
 - go faster
 - when finished assigned task or ready to continue: 'yes' (green tick icon)
 - when stuck or not finished: 'no' (cross icon)
- You can ask questions in the Zoom chat (use @helper) or in the Google Doc ****add link to the question header**** if they are not immediate or do not relate to the materials directly

Workshop website

****add link to website****

Pre-workshop survey

****add link to survey****

GS credits

- PhD candidates get 2 GS credits if they participate in the four days of the workshop:
- Sign in every day to receive the GS credits
- You will receive the Course Attendance form through CoachView

?Questions?

-
-
-
-
-
-

Day 1

Day 1 Programme

13:00 - Getting set up

13:15 - Welcome and introduction - ****add Coordinator name****

13:30 - Introduction to the Unix Shell - ****add Instructor name****

14:30 - Coffee break

14:45 - Automating tasks with the Unix Shell - ****add Instructor name****

15:45 - Coffee break

16:00 - Automating tasks with the Unix Shell - ****add Instructor name****

16:50 - Last questions and Feedback - ****add Coordinator name****

17:00 - End

Lessons: <http://swcarpentry.github.io/shell-novice/>

****add link to slides/materials****

Day 1 Roll Call

Name/ pronouns / job, role / faculty / social media (twitter) /
operating system / Graduate School Credits?

-
-
-
-
-
-
-

Day 1 Icebreaker

****insert question**** (If 2020 was a food, what would it be? What is
your favourite animal? Favourite season/command/ice cream?)

-
-
-
-
-
-

Why are you joining the workshop?

-
-
-
-
-

Editing permissions

For the rest of the workshop, you can change your editing
permissions of the document to suggesting/viewing to prevent
accidental deletion of the commands below:

Day 1 Commands

This section will contain all commands that are typed by ****add name****, with some explanation of what the command does.

You will need a few files for the exercises: <https://swcarpentry.github.io/shell-novice/setup.html>

this is a comment or explanation

\$this is a command

Feedback

Please provide your feedback ****add link to feedback document****.

Appendix C: Template for the post-workshop email to participants

Dear ****insert participant name****,

We are excited that you will be joining for the next Software Carpentry workshop this coming ****insert workshop dates****.

Before the workshop, there are some things that you will need to get ready:

- Be sure to complete the pre-workshop survey ****add link****. This is very important to help the instructors to calibrate the pace of the workshop.
- Please make sure you have a laptop available with a Mac, Linux, or Windows operating system (not a tablet, Chromebook, etc.). Make sure you have administrative privileges to it.
- Make sure you have the necessary software installed on your laptop and that you create a [GitHub account](#). You will find the list of software and installation instructions with videos here ****add link to the workshop website**** (scroll down for the set up section).

* If you experience any problems with the installations, please contact the instructors for Unix/Shell/Bash (instructor email ****add name and email****), Python (instructor email ****add name and email****) and Git (instructor email ****add name and email****).

For Python you can use [these verification instructions](#) to check if your installations are correct. Please contact the Python instructor if there are any errors/issues following these instructions.

- Make sure that you have downloaded the needed data sets on your laptop.
 - For the Unix-Shell lessons:
 1. Download data-shell.zip (<https://swcarpentry.github.io/shell-novice/data/data-shell.zip>) and move the file to your Desktop.
 2. Unzip/extract the file. You should end up with a new folder called **data-shell** on your Desktop.
 - For the Python lessons:

1. Download python-novice-inflammation-data.zip (<https://swcarpentry.github.io/python-novice-inflammation/data/python-novice-inflammation-data.zip>) and python-novice-inflammation-code.zip (<https://swcarpentry.github.io/python-novice-inflammation/code/python-novice-inflammation-code.zip>).
 2. Create a folder called swc-python on your Desktop.
 3. Move downloaded files to swc-python.
 4. Unzip the files.
 5. You should see two folders called data and code in the swc-python directory on your Desktop.
- Please read the [Carpentries Code of Conduct](#) so that we all are aware of how to treat each other respectfully.
 - Be aware that this is an **introductory** course. If you use programming (independently of the language) on a regular basis, you might want to review the Workshop Goals and workshop content on the website of the workshop [**add link to the workshop website**](#) before deciding to join.

Some practical info:

- **We have a very long waiting list of participants, so if you won't be able to attend, please let us know so we can offer your seat to someone else.**
 - ****insert information about who they should contact****
- The workshop will take place online via Zoom. We advise you to set up the meeting 5 min before the beginning of the workshop. The workshop can be accessed via the following links: ****insert the Zoom details****
- Please tell us if there is anything we should know in advance in order to make the workshop accessible for you (e.g. large-font on screen).

Please let us know if you have any questions.

Looking forward to seeing you soon!

Best,

Appendix D: Template for the post-workshop email to participants

Dear all,

Thanks again for attending the Software Carpentry Workshop! We hope you enjoyed the workshop and that you can apply it to your own research in the future!

#when screenshots are taken:

I attached the **pictures** that we took on Day 4. We may use this 'zoomfie' in a blog about the workshop: If you do not want your picture to be used for that purpose, please let me know! I'll blur the names in any case before posting it publicly.

The **lessons and materials** that we used during the workshop are available online:

- Day 1 / Shell: <http://swcarpentry.github.io/shell-novice/> (see the GitHub page here: <https://github.com/swcarpentry/shell-novice>)
- Day 2 and 3 / Python: <https://swcarpentry.github.io/python-novice-inflammation/index.html> (see the GitHub page here: <https://swcarpentry.github.io/python-novice-inflammation/>)
- Day 4 / Git/GitHub: <http://swcarpentry.github.io/git-novice/> (see the GitHub page here: <https://github.com/swcarpentry/git-novice>)

The materials contain a lot more information and extra exercises if you would like to practise more.

Here are some links to **materials** that may be of use:

- You can request a [GitLab instance from TU Delft](#). **GitLab** works similar to GitHub but the data will be stored on a location managed by TU Delft so it is safer for certain types of data in comparison to GitHub. If you have any questions regarding this you can always contact your Faculty's Data Steward!
- Please see the attachment for a **copy of the scripts that the instructor used for the Python lessons**.
- During the course we did not have time to discuss **licenses and documentation**:
 - When you make your data/code available you should select a license that will tell re-users of your outputs how they can reuse the work. If you have no idea what license you should select there's a [website with explanations on licenses in plain English](#). You can use the [Choose a License website](#) to find a license that suits your data/code. (If you want the shortcut, TU Delft recommends the MIT license for code and CC-BY for data.)

- o You can also listen to [this webinar on Open Software licenses](#), where they also discuss **readme files** (30.48 – 41:00), which you need for your project to describe it to others and tell them how to interact with your code/software.

Many thanks for all your feedback during the course! If you have not filled in the **post-workshop survey** yet, please do so here: ****add link to the workshop's post-workshop survey****.

The **Google Docs** ****add link to the collaborative notes**** will remain open so that you can come back to the materials. To ensure access to the doc you can also download your own copy (file > download). I now closed the edit rights, so if you would like to add/change anything it will appear in suggestion mode.

If you would like to take a more **intermediate programming** course you can keep an eye out for workshops organised by the Code Refinery team: <https://coderefinery.org/>. They have a notification list for any workshops they organise. We hope to organise another course like this at Delft but there are currently no confirmed dates for this.

If you run into troubles, or if a question popped up right after you left the workshop, you can [contact the Data Steward of your faculty](#) or you can send an email directly to the team of the [Digital Competence Center](#) to dcc@tudelft.nl.